

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D7.3

Robotics system integration (second version)

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACK	Acknowledgement message
API	Application Programming Interface
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
DMS	Data Management System
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
gRCS	Generic Robot Control Station
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
IVP	Intelligence and Visualization Portal
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging (sensor)
mRCS	Mission-specific Robot Control Station
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
PID	Proportional, Integral, Derivative (control)
PWM	Pulse-Width Modulation
RC	Remote Control
RCS	Robot Control Station
ROS	Robot Operating System
SDK	Software Development Kit
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
USB	Universal Serial Bus
VPN	Virtual Private Network
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

1. Introduction

One of PILOTING's technological objectives is the integration of diverse robotic systems using open interfaces and a scalable architecture. The PILOTING Inspection & Maintenance (I&M) platform will be integrated with nine different types of robot vehicles and applied to three scenarios (refineries, bridges/viaducts, and tunnels).

Following the iterative and incremental development strategy, the project is split in two main phases, each one being a complete development cycle composed of design, development, integration, testing and evaluation. This deliverable details the integration of the robotic systems in the second of these two development cycles.

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document is a description of the efforts that led to the integration of two key components of the PILOTING I&M platform:

- the generic Robot Control Station (gRCS), which standardizes the supervision of the robotic vehicles, and
- the robotic engine, which integrates the autonomous functionalities on the robotic vehicles.

It also includes experiments performed at laboratory or controlled environments, to validate such integration. In addition, since this deliverable corresponds to the second cycle of integration, some experiments have been performed in more realistic environments.

This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within tasks T7.1 ("Ground and crawler robotic systems integration") and T7.2 ("Aerial and hybrid robotic system integration"). It is also the continuation of deliverable D7.1, which describes the first integration cycle. Multiple references to D7.1 are made in this document to avoid duplication of information.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows.

- Section 2 describes the work done for the integration with the robotic vehicles from the gRCS.
- Section 3 details the integration of the software development for each robotic vehicle and their communication with the gRCS.
- Section 4 describes the experiments performed in controlled or even in realistic environments to validate the integrations.
- Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions.

2. Generic Robot Control Station Integration

From the gRCS point of view, the integration between it and the different robotic vehicles has been carried out following the communication protocol defined in deliverable “D6.1 General robot control station (first version)”. Following the information in this deliverable, different sequences of messages were established, as well as their format and content.

On the other hand, in the previous deliverable D7.1 it was established how to integrate this communication protocol, developing a MAVLink library that includes all the definitions already made. With this library, another C++ library was prepared to serve as an abstraction layer for present and future robotic platforms that want to integrate with the gRCS of the PILOTING ecosystem. This library is called PILOTING-MAVSDK and is available in open-source¹ following Open Data Access guidelines from the EC. Its API and implementation were detailed in section 2.1.1 of deliverable D7.1.

In addition to the C++ implementation, we have been working on a wrapper for ROS that executes the same functionalities but with different interfaces: through ROS topics and services. This new implementation was called PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS and is also available in open-source².

These two implementations have proven to work very well during the first phase of platform integration, as well as the second one presented in this paper. Since the beginning of this second phase, the libraries have not undergone any changes at the interface level, so their development has been validated.

However, in order to improve the functioning of the communication protocols between the gRCS and the robotic platforms, small corrections have been made to the messages already defined, or even some new ones that were not taken into account have been included. All these changes have already been described in section 3.1 of deliverable D6.5, so in order to avoid duplication of information they will not be described again here.

¹ https://github.com/fada-catec/piloting_mavsdk

² <https://github.com/fada-catec/piloting-mavsdk-ros>

3. Robotic Engine Integration

This section describes the software integration of all robotic platforms through their robotic engines. As in the previous deliverable D7.1, this integration includes the software to operate the autonomous functionalities and establish communication and data transfer with the gRCS and therefore, the PILOTING ecosystem. On this occasion, we have focused our efforts on describing the updates from the previous deliverable and not repeating the modules already described that have not undergone major changes. In addition, this section does not intend to describe in detail the stand-alone functionalities, but to give information about their implementation and interfaces.

3.1 Aerial Robots

3.1.1 AEROX

The AEROX platform takes on the responsibility of conducting refinery pipe inspections using a sensor that makes physical contact with the surface of the infrastructure. This section provides an overview of the software developed and integrated into the robotic engine.

The provided image displays the revised main block diagram, illustrating all the interconnected systems and their relationships (Physical borders as dotted lines, data flow as solid lines, functionalities grouped by colors).

Figure 1. AEROX general diagram block.

The layout diagram of AEROX has undergone a significant upgrade compared to its previous version. The key change is the reorganization of computing tasks between two separate computers, connected through a gigabit Ethernet connection. This separation allows mission-critical and demanding processes to operate without computational setbacks that could occur in a more overloaded single board configuration. Additionally, this upgrade improves cable management and paves the way for incorporating new computational features.

The software integration has transitioned from a MATLAB/ROS-based architecture to a predominantly C/C++ environment. ROS now plays a limited role, primarily acting as the final link between ground computers, the gRCS (Ground Control Station), and other ROS nodes that may be used (see Figure 1). This shift to a C/C++ environment enhances the software's performance and flexibility, while still leveraging the connectivity and functionality provided by ROS for specific communication and coordination tasks.

Onboard cameras

In the latest AEROX version, no stereo cameras are used. Instead, an FPV camera in the RMCP aids the commanding technician to see the contact surface.

Total position estimator

In cases where it is necessary for the mission, additional components can be utilized to establish a correlation between the UT measurements and their corresponding positions on the inspected asset. These components include a Leica total station and a compatible position estimator. The position estimator collects data from both the AEROX onboard server and the Leica prism tracking system. As a result, the coordinates obtained can be conveniently visualized in the gRCS, providing a comprehensive and precise representation of the data.

UAV Control

In the latest upgrade, MATLAB no longer hosts any tasks. The main PID controller and state machine are now fully embedded in a C/C++ environment. A high-level application (represented by the blue blocks in Figure 1) manages all AEROX tasks from the avionics level. The datalink between the platform and the gRCS is integrated using a MAVSDK ROS node, with an additional WebSocket server in the AEROX master application for relaying data to and from internal processes.

3.1.2 AERO-CAM

The AERO-CAM aerial robotic platform is in charge of performing a visual inspection of the viaducts. This platform was fully integrated into the PILOTING system, as described in section 3.1.2 of deliverable D7.1. During the various preliminary experiments and the first pilots performed, everything worked as expected at the integration level. Therefore, the AERO-CAM system has not undergone any profound changes during this period.

Figure 2 shows the updated AERO-CAM block diagram.

Figure 2. AERO-CAM general diagram block.

As in the previous deliverable, the processes running inside the onboard computers (Intel NUCi7 and Raspberry Pi) make use of ROS for communication between them through topics and processes. In addition, the ground computer used for mRCS and global localization also uses it. On the other hand, the gRCS uses the Mavlink communication protocol through the MAVSDK library.

The main updates are the following:

Global Localization

The global localization has undergone a major change to move this processing node from the onboard Intel NUCi7 to the ground computer where the mRCS runs. This decision was motivated by the high computational load required by this node. The onboard computer, when performing critical processing for aircraft navigation, can become overloaded in certain situations. Therefore, since real-time processing is not required, this node has been moved to a ground computer where there is plenty of processing capacity.

Global localization then depends on sending through the LIDAR point cloud communications link, primarily. This link can have delays as it is a large amount of data that must be compressed and sent in packets over wireless communication, then recomposed and processed. This delay has been considered by sending the time stamp of the moment the point cloud is generated, being able to publish the location result at that time in the past.

This change has been validated in the experiments performed since the publication of the previous deliverable and has shown good results, relieving the computational burden on the on-board computer.

Obstacle Detection

The obstacle detection node has been introduced from the onboard computer. This process is subscribed directly through ROS to the LIDAR point cloud and UAV velocity. The obstacles detected around the UAV through the point cloud analysis are sent to the Mission Manager and mRCS to be plotted.

Sony Camera Bridge

The main update to this node has been the successive release by the manufacturer of new versions of the SDK used to control the camera. The node code has been updated to take advantage of all the improvements. Now the data transfer between the camera and the onboard computer is done more efficiently, transmitting the images in small packets and releasing the camera earlier, so you can take pictures with less time between them. In addition, the various configuration parameters can be saved and loaded from a file, allowing you to set the desired settings from the start.

Finally, the rest of the nodes have not undergone significant changes. The AERO-CAM platform is fully integrated in the PILOTING ecosystem receiving inspection plans with position waypoints, visual inspection waypoints and visual inspection areas, as shown in Figure 3, and executing them.

Figure 3. AERO-CAM inspection plan (including points and areas) in the Piloting portal.

3.1.3 VIAD-DRONE

The general block diagram of the software has suffered minor changes with respect to the system presented in section 3.1.3 of D7.1, due to the good results obtained in the PILOTING integrated experiments performed in 2022. The most relevant one is related to the Inspection Camera, which is now controlled by a new ROS driver instead of by the Add-ons Driver. In this way, inspection images are directly stored in the onboard computer allowing the automatic generation of post-mission data.

On the other hand, the implementation of the Mission Manager has been completed. This module is now able to receive a mission from the gRCS, plan robot specific actions to fulfil the tasks and execute them automatically. The procedure to design a mission and the planning performed by the robot is detailed as follows.

Asset Model and Inspection Locations

The design of a mission requires the previous generation of an asset model. Once the model has been generated and loaded into the IVP, the Inspection Locations can be established also within the portal. These locations must be points associated with the bearings to be inspected or the points to perform installations. After that, the Inspection Locations can be included in an Inspection Plan the gRCS can download and which is used to establish the waypoints of the mission. Figure 4 and Figure 5 show an example of Inspection Locations defined for the different use cases and an Inspection Plan created for a visual inspection, respectively.

Figure 4. Example of Inspection Locations for VIAD-DRONE defined within the IVP.

Figure 5. Example of an Inspection Plan generated for the Bearing Inspection use case.

Waypoints

After the creation of an Inspection Plan, it can be downloaded into the gRCS to then define the waypoints the robot must follow. The types of waypoints available in the gRCS are Pose waypoints and Action waypoints. Action waypoints are always placed over an Inspection Location and are related to a task to be performed. Pose waypoints are points of the asset to which the robot must fly in order of arrival. However, they are also included before or after Action waypoints to provide the robot with information about the geometry of the viaduct. Those Pose waypoints are not followed by the robot as standard waypoints; they will only be used to plan the tasks associated with the Action waypoints.

To allow the classification of standard Pose waypoints and those to provide geometrical information, a simple and intuitive protocol is used for the order of the waypoints. Every time a waypoint list is sent to the robot, it checks that the list of waypoints follows the rules established to define an inspection mission. If the waypoint list does not follow the rule, the robot sends the gRCS details to facilitate the detection and correction of the error. The operation of the VIAD-DRONE planner module (already presented in deliverable D7.1) is slightly different for each use case. The operation of the planner for the different VIAD-DRONE is summarized below.

Bearing Inspection Task

Planning a bearing inspection task requires three waypoints. The first one is a contact waypoint, to which the robot attaches. Contact waypoints are Pose waypoints whose Z axis points down, whereas standard Pose waypoints always have their Z axis pointing up. These waypoints must be followed by two Action waypoints associated to the bearings to be inspected. After the robot attaches to the contact waypoint, it crawls towards the middle point between the viaduct bearings while keeping the contact with the viaduct deck. The robot stops at a configurable distance from the middle point and then takes the required inspection pictures. Figure 6 shows a graphical representation of the planning performed by the robot. Two cases are shown. In one of them (Figure 6-top), the contact waypoint is located at the central part of the deck. In the other, see Figure 6-bottom, the contact waypoint is not located at the central part of the deck. The operation of the planner module is flexible to the location of the contact waypoint on the deck surface.

Figure 6. Planning performed by VIAD-DRONE robot for bearing inspections in two examples.

Sensor Box Installation Task

To perform a sensor box installation, a similar planning is performed. However, in this case, there is a single Action waypoint in which the robot must install the box. As shown in Figure 7, the robot crawls towards and up to the Action point to perform the installation there. Both cases, the contact waypoint is (and not) located at the central part of the deck are shown.

Figure 7. Planning performed by the robot for sensor box installations.

Target Installation Task

Lastly, to perform a target installation, the robot needs the orientation of the wall to face it before the sticking of the target. Therefore, a Pose Waypoint with its Z axis perpendicular to the wall and pointing outside the pillar must be included after the Action waypoint which establishes the installation point. With this information, before performing the maneuver, the robot flies to a waypoint at a configurable distance in front of the installation point as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Planning performed by VIAD-DRONE for target installations.

3.1.4 TTDRONE

The software architecture of the TTDRONE is similar to the VIAD-DRONE. In this case, the general diagram of the modules is also almost the same as the previously described in section 3.1.4 of D7.1. The principal change is also the addition of a dedicated ROS driver for the inspection camera which allows automatic post-mission data generation.

The implementation of the Mission Manager for the TTDRONE has also been completed allowing the automatic planning and execution of missions designed with the IVP and the gRCS.

Asset Model and Inspection Locations

The placement of the Inspection Locations in the asset model with the IVP is done similarly as in the VIAD-DRONE missions. Nevertheless, in this case the Inspection Locations will be associated with the points to be visually inspected. Figure 9 shows an example of an asset model with previously defined Inspection Locations and in which an Inspection Plan is being designed. After that, the Inspection Plan could be downloaded into the gRCS to establish the waypoints of the mission and start its execution.

Figure 9. Example of the definition of an Inspection Plan for TTDRONE.

Waypoints

The list of waypoints sent to the robot are generated with the gRCS after the download of the previously generated Inspection Plan. When the TTDRONE receives the list of waypoints of the mission, it manages the Pose waypoints and Actions waypoints in the same way as the VIAD-DRONE. As commented in the previous section, Action waypoints must be sent together with the Pose waypoints to provide information about the geometry of the environment, in this case, the tunnel.

Tunnel Local Inspection Task

The visual inspection of the tunnel defects requires placing the camera in front of them at a certain distance. To perform the planning, the normal vector of the tunnel wall must correspond to the Z axis of a Pose waypoint included after the Action waypoint associated with the defect to be inspected. Figure 10 shows how the pose to perform the inspection would be calculated.

Figure 10. Planning performed by the robot for tunnel local inspections.

3.2 Ground Robots

3.2.1 *RISING and CART*

It is important to recall how the Robotic Engine Integration matters are mostly shared between the Robotnik robots used in PILOTING, both RISING and CART, due to the shared software architecture based in ROS.

The details on this integration were already discussed detailed in section deliverable D7.1. While there are no major changes made to this architecture a lot of details and improvements have been taken care of since the first validation tests.

Localization and Model generation

In the case of the tunnel inspection, some features have been reworked regarding some inherent aspects of the inspection as the model generation or the localization with regards to this model.

As a first remark, the robotic system is now able to support different types of localization feeds, including the SINTEF navigation payload for GNSS denied environments, the enhanced RB-CAR odometry and a modified 3D slam based on Cartographer tool.

Since localization challenge is normally coupled with map generation, the map is also usually generated by SINTEF payload, but the map can also be recorded with Cartographer or even with third

party tools such as dedicated reality capture devices (i.e. LEICA BLK) as long as the alignment of the map with the waypoint coordinate system is done prior the start of the inspection. A specific node interpolating points and “translating” pose estimation is also in place for that.

Figure 11. Tunnel model of Coripe generated by SINTEF payload.

Coming to the ground robot monitoring case, a similar localization and navigation challenge has been addressed with the support of ETHZ Moma navigation package, which was deployed and tested successfully in Robotnik RISING robot.

Figure 12. Rising robotic platform in RViz while launching MOMA docker.

Inspection Definition, parameters and internal nodes

For both cases the PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS and then the robotnik_mavros packages are playing an important role on dealing with waypoints, poses and actions.

In this sense, a specific development for the RB-CAR has been implemented dealing with the continuous data capture and the segment inspection definition in the IVP. This need was identified during the first validation pilots and came with several modifications to the robotnik_mavros package dealing with the sequence of actions.

Such a feature required dedicated changes on how the pipeline from the IVP to the gRCS and then to the robot is working. Some development to handle the process at internal level also needed a parametrization of the messages. As a short summary we can highlight the steps and requirements:

1. The CART handles internally the navigation following the tunnel wall and the triggering of the camera every certain distance.
2. For a full coverage of the tunnel in a mission no specific waypoints are given but an area to be inspected. This can also be defined with a “Segment” feature of the IVP which defines a prim and its intersection with the tunnel point cloud, as shown in Figure 13.
3. The position of the lifting column and the gimbal is given through the parameters of actions define in the gRCS. This can also be done with an initial and final position for each pass of the RB-CAR

Again, the internal nodes had to be reworked to handle the navigation sequence, triggering, autocontinue and positioning of the sensors.

Figure 13. Tunnel Inspection Segment feature.

Lidar inspection

At first triggering the inspection with a Lidar was an internal process triggered with a local interface. In the last updates of the system, a “Lidar inspection request” was added to the whole pipeline starting from the IVP. The FARO API has been used to create an internal interface to the RB-CAR, also considering timeframes and position information exchange.

DMS formatting and extension to new robots

Following the initial integration works, different solutions and enhancements were agreed to fix the data structure of the missions generated by the ground robots. This included a revision to the sensors being used and how the data was stored and acknowledged.

It can also be highlighted that this exercise made possible the extension to other robots with the same architecture and sensors, such as the RB-Watcher robot that could be deployed for the “ground monitoring” use case.

3.2.2 UGV

The UGV was built for autonomous inspection and manipulation in refinery environments. In particular, valve manipulation tasks are conducted by means a 7-DoF robot manipulation arm. The same command triggering infrastructure and communication that was originally intended for RISING and discussed in detail in D7.1 applies. Thus, we will only highlight additional implementations and interfaces that were required on top for the UGV.

To make the PILOTING platform aware of the robot, the UGV had to be added to the DMS. In collaboration with INLECOM, all sensors and other relevant hardware was added to the database. In this context, the DMS also generated unique identifiers for the UGV and all its sensors, which are used as a reference in all communication concerning the DMS.

For successful mission execution, reliable and safe communication with the gRCS had to be established. In terms of integration with the gRCS, multiple integration rounds were completed. Also, the data acquisition and uploading of inspection data to the DMS via the DDHL was addressed.

First, the specification of the MAVSDK-ROS package provided by CATEC was analyzed. It is a wrapper around the well-known MAVSDK protocol for MAVLink systems that simplifies the integration and interfacing with the ROS ecosystem of the UGV. Based on this analysis, the required commands and corresponding parameters specific to the inspection and maintenance tasks executed by the UGV were defined. In particular, the commands for the manipulation of valves, the capturing of photos and the reading of pressure gauges were specified. Following this definition, an interface handler for the protocol that can respond to all the relevant commands was implemented on the UGV. To provide a suitable bridge between the gRCS and the robot's low-level actions, an internal state machine was implemented on the UGV as an intermediate layer. This state machine depends on the current hardware and software state of the UGV and handles all the commands received via MAVSDK-ROS. In contrast to a direct, unfiltered execution of the commands sent to the robot, this state machine acts as a safety and control layer and prevents the execution of actions for which the robot is not ready. It also allows for a controlled stop of command execution. Depending on the success of the individual steps of the state machine, feedback is given via MAVSDK-ROS back to the gRCS.

Figure 14. UGV integration pipeline high-level architecture overview.

In a second phase, the implementations were verified on a local simulation of the UGV in Zurich by means of a VPN connection to CATEC in Spain, running the gRCS on the remote end. During this phase, the responses of the UGV to the commands sent by CATEC were reviewed and verified. Furthermore, due to the latency and increased round-trip times introduced by the VPN connection between two locally different sites, a realistic communication scenario found under imperfect communication channels in real refinery environments could be simulated. This was particularly important in order to adjust and verify implementation parameters such as timeouts in the communication protocol.

Finally, a recording and format conversion software was developed, in order to record the entire robotic mission locally on the UGV and convert it to the file format specified and required by the DDHL. The correct format and upload process of simulated mission data could successfully be verified by means of an iterative process, including uploading recorded simulated mission data and inspecting the converted and stored DMS data by means of the IVP.

Figure 15. DDHL upload format after UGV internal format conversion.

3.3 Crawlers and Hybrid Robots

3.3.1 BIKE

BIKE control integration was detailed in section 3.3.1 of deliverable D7.1. Since the integration and the robot control worked as expected, no fundamental changes were made after the field validation testing. There were however a few features missing in the integration, which were subsequently added to the robot specific control software.

Asset Model and Inspection Locations

Every asset to be inspected with the BIKE needs to be modeled in the PILOTING portal. All inspection locations with associated inspection methods/actions are also defined in the portal as shown by Figure 16.

Figure 16. Asset with inspection locations.

Inspection Plan

The inspection plan is created for the asset in the portal by assigning the corresponding inspection method and an inspection order to a relevant subset of the inspection locations. Figure 17 shows the resulting inspection plan. Each task is either a visual inspection task, an ultrasonic spot measurement task or an ultrasonic raster/area inspection task.

Figure 17. BIKE inspection plan.

Waypoints

After the inspection plan is downloaded to the gRCS software, a mission specific waypoint list is created by the robot operator. The operator can add so-called “pose-waypoints” which serve the purpose of guiding the robot or to align it for a specific activity. They then can directly click on the actions / tasks and include them as so-called “action waypoints” into the waypoint list. Figure 18 shows how the inspection plan is shown in the gRCS user interface to the operator. Figure 19 shows the final waypoint list with details and Figure 20 shows the graphical representation of the waypoint list in the form it is later used to execute the mission.

Figure 18. BIKE inspection plan as downloaded to gRCS software, showing the environment model as well as the inspection locations and tasks.

Waypoints Editor														
Route Id	AutoCont	SeqN	Task UUID	PosX (m)	PosY (m)	PosZ (m)	Roll (°)	Pitch (°)	Yaw (°)	Param1	Param2	Param3	Param4	Type
▼ 1														
	✓	0	b11...e47	0.978	0.063	-0.893	-0.582	-5.244	94.227	---	---	---	---	POSE
	✓	1	b11...e47	0.817	0.899	0.011	---	---	---	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	ACTION
	✓	2	6e7...a22	1.210	0.000	0.910	---	---	---	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	ACTION
	✓	3	6e7...a22	0.988	0.695	0.542	-1...70	-51.752	-9...04	---	---	---	---	POSE
	✓	4	6e7...a22	1.155	-0.718	0.507	1...9	36.475	-1...19	---	---	---	---	POSE
	✓	5	558...03e	0.813	-0.891	0.009	---	---	---	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	ACTION
	✓	6	f55...b6d	1.167	-0.799	-0.270	---	---	---	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	ACTION
	✓	7	f55...b6d	1.022	-0.437	-0.762	29.005	0.514	17...33	---	---	---	---	POSE
	✓	8	7fa...1c3	0.000	0.000	0.000	---	---	---	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	ACTION
	✓	9	7fa...1c3	1.380	-0.022	-0.886	-2.705	1.554	-0.037	---	---	---	---	POSE

Figure 19. Waypoints editor user interface in gRCS.

Figure 20. Finished waypoint-list in gRCS software, showing the different waypoints and connecting lines indicating the execution order for BIKE.

Visual Inspection Tasks

Once the robot specific control software is connected, the operator can command the robot to move to any of the defined waypoints. Usually this would be done by increasing the waypoint index by one in order to stick to the pre-allocated inspection order.

When the robot control software receives a waypoint index associated to an action waypoint and the action is visual inspection, the robot automatically tries to aim the inspection camera at the associated point of interest.

The qualified inspector (expert) is then free to immediately capture the image or to adjust both, camera and robot position as well as capturing multiple images.

Ultrasonic Inspection Tasks

When the robot control software receives a waypoint index associated to an action waypoint and the action is UT inspection, the robot automatically stops at the waypoint location.

The qualified inspector (expert) is then free to immediately capture the wall thickness or to adjust the robot position as well as to capture multiple thickness readings from that location. Every capture should directly contain the thickness value. The recorded A-scan data can be attached to the capture directly or after mission completion.

If the task associated to the UT waypoint is a raster scan, the operator can configure the raster pattern and record the UT data. The recorded C-scan data can be attached to the capture directly or after mission completion.

3.3.2 HYBRID

The HYBRID platform is the union of a UAV and the SATELLITE robot for landing on and contact inspection of pipelines.

In the previous deliverable, it was exposed that the HYBRID aerial robot consisted of a sensor system similar to AEROCAM but using mirrors in the lidar to detect the pipes and perform the localization relative to it with this sensor. However, during a series of tests in realistic environments, it was concluded that these mirrors did not achieve the required accuracy. This is because when the platform is in the final stages of landing on the pipeline it is not able to detect it correctly with this configuration. That is why we have chosen to change the configuration as proposed in the current section.

Figure 21 shows the general diagram of the blocks implemented in the aerial robot part of the HYBRID. On the left, those marked in green are sensors or external data connected to the platform. The aerial robot part of HYBRID has an onboard computer Intel NUCi7. In addition, one of the major changes is the use of CATEC's own autopilot instead of a commercial one. This will be described later.

Figure 21. HYBRID general diagram block.

As well as AERO-CAM and most of the robotic vehicles, the processes running inside the onboard computers make use of ROS. The communications with the gRCS are done through MAVSDK library.

The most relevant blocks of the diagram are explained below:

- **URG Node Driver**

The main purpose of this driver is to translate the measurements received via Ethernet from the sensor to ROS messages. Specifically, the message used is *sensor_msgs/LaserScan* and the information will

be received at 10 Hz. To do this, the driver makes use of the URG library developed by the manufacturers of the sensor, Hokuyo Automatic Co that is written in C.

- **Librealsense Driver**

This driver manages the communication with the onboard RGB-D camera via USB 3.0. For capturing the data from the sensors *librealsense* library is used. This library will allow the application of presets over the sensor to adjust its operation to the working environment as well as to receive the information from the camera. Specifically, it will publish the point cloud generated by the sensor at 30 Hz using the ROS topic type *sensor_msgs/PointCloud2*.

- **CATEC AP UDP ROS Bridge**

The purpose of this module is to manage the communication between the CATEC Autopilot and the onboard computer. The physical connection is through an ethernet interface, and the communications will be done through UDP sockets.

Fixed structures associated with each type of ROS message to be sent have been defined and, in this way, the information between the autopilot and ROS can be generically parsed. A communication socket will be opened over which all information is exchanged and, based on a common types definition file, data will be converted. Additionally, by making use of the intrinsic nature of the UDP protocol, the correct exchange of information is ensured. The implementation of this driver has been done in C++ and with *Boost Asio* sockets.

- **CATEC Autopilot**

The CATEC Autopilot is based on QNX Real Time Operating system running in a custom hardware which also integrates two auxiliar microcontrollers running on Free RTOS operating system. Each module in the autopilot aims to achieve a specific task as listed below:

- Auxiliar IO Controller provides data from RC Receiver and generates the actuations as PWM signals.
- Auxiliar FMU Controller provides sensing data from auxiliar components which may be fitted to the platform.
- Main SOM executes the RTOS Kernell and the necessary tasks to provide Guidance, Navigation and Control schemes to the platform and manages the communication between all the components.

All applications running at the CATEC Autopilot employ C and C++ languages in the framework of fully tested and commercial compilers, ensuring a high level of reliability and safety during operation.

The following diagram shows the interaction between the components as a top view of the complete Autopilot subsystem:

Figure 22. CATEC's autopilot components.

- **Relative Localization**

The relative location block works in the same way as in the AERO-CAM platform. It uses on-board sensors to obtain high frequency odometry from an arbitrary point in space, such as the takeoff point. It receives as input the reading from the LIDAR and IMU sensors and has as output a 6 DoF pose.

- **Global Localization**

The global localization runs on a ground computer and communicates with the robotic platform through a wireless connection, making use of the ROS protocol. This block establishes the correspondence between the relative location with the reference map obtained with the total station, as in the AERO-CAM platform.

- **Pipes Detector**

The purpose of this block is to detect the pipes relative to the sensors used. In other words, to detect the pipes with respect to the HYBRID's base frame. To do this, two sensors are used: on the one hand the 2D laser and on the other hand the depth camera. Through the depth camera, a portion of the pipe is obtained. Although it presents some noise, it helps to estimate the characteristics of the pipe. The 2D laser only provides us with the pipe section, but it is very accurate. This is why it has been decided to work with these two sensors together.

- **Pipes Real-Time Data Base**

This module has a double purpose: on the one hand, it is responsible for transforming the pipes detections from the HYBRID's base frame to the take-off location relative reference frame. On the other hand, it is in charge of merging the different pipes estimates to have a complete view of the

pipes and not only of a single section or portion of the pipeline. In addition, it merges the estimations of the sensors used to detect them.

So, for each detected pipe, this module creates a linear Kalman Filter to track them over time. Also, for each new detected pipe, the module decides whether to create a new pipe on the real-time database or to update an existing one. This also allows filtering possible noise in the detections as well as to have a global conception of the pipe and not only local to the sensor.

- **State Machine**

The purpose of this module is to organize and control the different actions and tasks of the aerial robot describing a set of finite states and the transition between them as shown in the Figure 23. The State Machine does not have control over the purple blocks. Green blocks are safe states while the blue ones are risk states because they are carried out autonomously.

Transitions between manual and offboard are always handled by a remote pilot who is supervising constantly the operation while the transitions inside the Offboard Block are handled by itself due to conditions that trigger those transitions.

Figure 23. HYBRID state machine.

Regarding the communications, this block needs receiving continuous messages from the *Relative Localization* and the *CATEC AP UDP ROS Bridge*. Targeted pipe messages from *Mission Manager* are only received when a pipe is detected. It sends constant command messages to *CATEC AP UDP ROS Bridge*.

- **Mission Manager**

The objective of this module is to manage the mission of the HYBRID's aerial robot. On the one hand, it is in charge of communications with the gRCS. Also, on the other hand, it manages the creation of the specific mission to carry out the autonomous functionalities. Figure 24 shows a diagram of this module, through which its functionality will be explained.

Figure 24. HYBRID mission manager diagram block.

Regarding the communication with the gRCS and, by extension, with the I&M portal, this is done through the previously described library in the previous sections, PILOTING-MAVSDK-ROS. Through this interface, as in all other robotic vehicles, all mission data exchanges take place.

On the one hand, the Inspection Plan generated in the I&M portal is sent from the gRCS to the robotic vehicle. On the other hand, multiple information is sent from the robotic vehicle to the gRCS: the telemetry of the robotic vehicle in a global reference frame (ENU), the robot specific alarms, as well as the high-level actions and the check list to be filled in by the gRCS operator before performing the inspection.

To transform the odometry, 6 DoF pose and velocity, estimated by the robotic vehicle to a global reference frame, it is necessary to make use of global localization. The mission manager takes the relative and global location, sending to the gRCS the telemetry in the appropriate frame of reference.

In addition, using the Inspection Plan received, the mission manager is responsible for generating the route to be followed by the aerial robot to land on the desired pipe. For this purpose, an obstacle-free route to the target pipe surroundings is generated. During the execution of the autonomous mission, this route is refined by making use of the stable detections provided by the real-time pipes database. An association is made between the pipes detected by the on-board sensors of the robotic vehicle with the desired landing position received from the I&M portal. In this way, the landing position can be fine-tuned and rectified in real time to achieve a safe landing on the pipeline.

Finally, the mission manager takes care of the communication with the robotic vehicle's state machine. It is responsible for sending the landing pose to the state machine, so that it can manage the communications with the aircraft control and be able to carry out the operation autonomously. In addition, it is also in charge of receiving the commands sent through the high-level actions of the gRCS and responding with the corresponding ACKs. As well as reporting certain alarms from the aircraft's autopilot flight information, such as battery level or the status of the aerial robot.

4. Integration Validation in Controlled Environments

In this section we describe the integration of the robotic platforms with the gRCS and the various tests performed. As in the previous document (D7.1), all integrations have been performed with the software developed for the robotic platforms described in section 3. Due to the maturity of the developments in this part of the project, many validations have been performed not only in simulation, but with the real robotic platform. In addition, since access to real environments has been available for testing, many validations have been performed in the field, after validation in the laboratory.

The gRCS integration plan is the same as in the previous deliverable. The functionalities are separated by blocks and ordered by blocks of importance and difficulty of implementation:

- **Heartbeat:** the basic capability to make a connection between the gRCS and the robotic platform.
- **Telemetry:** be able to send position and orientation information to the gRCS, as well as status text messages.
- **Navigation:** be able to receive a list of waypoints, process it, and execute it giving feedback to the gRCS on the progress of the mission. Be able to change the current waypoint at the request of the gRCS.
- **Commands:** be able to process and execute commands sent from the gRCS.

For the previous deliverable, an isolated executable was provided for each of the functionalities described above. These executables simulated the gRCS and simplified the whole process. However, given the maturity of the developments, this deliverable has been validated with the gRCS itself. This has been distributed to partners through a Docker image, which simplifies the installation process.

The integration of robotic systems has also been validated with the real platforms during the PILOTING experiments in the project timeline, performing the full workflow. This validates not only the robot integration with gRCS, but also the compatibility with the rest of the PILOTING ecosystem. These validations have consisted of the following steps, bringing an integration procedure:

1. Create an Inspection Plan with the IVP.
2. Create a list of waypoints with the gRCS to fulfil the tasks specified in the Inspection Plan.
3. Execute an autonomous mission from the gRCS with the real platform.
4. Upload post-mission data from the gRCS and the robots.
5. Visualize uploaded data in IVP.

The following subsections describe the current status of integrations for each type of robotic vehicle:

4.1 Aerial Robots

The status of the integration of aerial robotic platforms is as follows:

Table 1. Aerial robots - gRCS integration status.

System	Heartbeat	Telemetry	Navigation	Command	Comments
AEROX	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 1st cycle. Validated in 1st pilots at Álora (Jul 22). Validated again during 2 nd integration cycle
AERO-CAM	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 1st cycle. Validated in 1st pilots at Chevron Oronite (Sep 22). Validated again during 2 nd integration cycle
VIAD-DRONE	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 1st cycle. Validated in 1st pilots at Álora (Jul 22). Validated again during 2 nd integration cycle
TTDRONE	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 1st cycle. Validated in 1st pilots at Álora (Jul 22). Validated again during 2 nd integration cycle

The validation of the AERO-CAM platform was extensively explained in the previous deliverable D7.1, and the first pilot experiments of the project validated the integration of the AERO-CAM platform. On the other hand, the AEROX platform was also integrated in the first cycle, although for simplicity's sake no details were introduced in the previous deliverable. This integration was also validated in the first pilot experiments, as illustrated in Figure 25, where the gRCS is shown with the AEROX performing an inspection of a tank. Finally, it is important to mention that for both platforms, AEROX and AEROCAM, a number of tests have been performed during the second integration phase to validate that everything was still working as in the first pilot experiments.

Figure 25. gRCS view of AEROX inspecting a tank in the first pilots.

On the other hand, the integration of the VIAD-DRONE and the TTDRONE platforms with the gRCS, and the PILOTING framework in general, was initially validated similarly as detailed in section 4.1 of D7.1 for the AERO-CAM robotic system. The tests were performed with simulated platforms to allow the development and the debugging of the system concurrently with the development of the localization and of the autonomous functionalities associated to each use case.

Both robotic systems (VIAD-DRONE and TTDRONE) were able to communicate with the gRCS. The localization estimated by the robots was sent to the gRCS, which was successfully visualized in the telemetry widget and in the 3D representation together with the model of the environment. The robots were able to manage the commands sent with the gRCS to set the home pose and to perform high-level actions. The ability of the robots to receive a waypoint list, ensure its proper format and execute the missions autonomously planned was also successfully validated. Figure 26 shows the messages received in the gRCS after the sending of two wrong waypoint lists and a correct one to perform a bearing inspection. As shown, the robot refused both wrong missions, providing an explanation of the problem.


```

[16:50:55] (INFO) Successfully loaded asset
[16:51:27] (INFO) Waiting 1 second to establish connection after define IPs and ports...
[16:51:28] (INFO) Target system (30) connected!
[16:51:28] (INFO) Connection to robotics system successfully
[16:51:28] (INFO) Successfully waypoint list download with size: 0
[16:51:30] (ERROR) Mission not compatible, there are no CONTACT waypoints
[16:51:30] (WARN) The waypoint list cannot be uploaded due to: Upload waypoint list error ack: Error
[16:51:43] (WARN) The waypoint list cannot be uploaded due to: Upload waypoint list error ack: Error
[16:51:43] (ERROR) Mission not compatible, each CONTACT waypoint (z axis pointing to the ground) must be followed by 2 ACTION waypoints
[16:52:21] (INFO) Successfully waypoint list upload: Accepted
  
```

Figure 26. gRCS console output after sending a set of missions to VIAD-DRONE.

The missions were successfully executed, and no problems were reported with mission parsing and planning and with the feedback visualized in the gRCS. Post-mission data related to both platforms and for each type of mission possible with them (installations and visual inspections) was uploaded and visualized in the IVP. Figure 27 shows the post-mission data generated and uploaded by the VIAD-DRONE robot after a mission for a target installation. When the mission involves pictures, after the sending of the post-mission data, the location from where they were taken can be visualized together with the robot trajectory in the IVP. All inspection pictures can be visualized as well. Figure 28 shows an example for a Tunnel Local Inspection with the TTDRONE.

Figure 27. Post-mission data generated by VIAD-DRONE and available at IVP.

Figure 28. Post-mission generated by TTDRONE and visualized at IVP.

Also, it is important to mention that for both platforms, TTDRONE and VIAD-DRONE, a number of tests have been performed during the second integration phase to validate that everything was still working as in the first pilot experiments.

4.2 Ground Robots

The status of the integration of ground robotic platforms is as follows:

Table 2. Ground Robots - gRCS integration status.

System	Heartbeat	Telemetry	Navigation	Command	Comments
RISING	✓	✓	✓	✓	Almost completely validated in 1 st pilots at Chevron Oronite (Sep 22) and fully integrated and validated in the 2 nd cycle.
CART	✓	✓	✓	✓	Almost completely validated in 1 st pilots at EGNATIA Metsovo (Sep 22) and fully integrated in the 2 nd cycle. Fully validated during 2 nd integration cycle in a realistic environment (Coripe tunnel)
UGV	✓	✓	✓	✓	Validated in 1 st pilots at Chevron Oronite (Sep 22) and fully integrated in the 2 nd cycle. Validated again during 2 nd integration cycle

The validation of the integration process was initially conducted within 2022 pilots on-site, in both CHEVRON refinery facilities for the ground monitoring case and EGNATIA Metsovo tunnel for the tunnel inspection case. For both cases, a detailed results insight is given in D8.1.

In the case of the ground monitoring with the RISING robotic platform, the validation experiments were performed in the Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France. The experiment area was a multi-level decommissioned process module housing a mix of process piping and vessels.

Details on the performance of the robot can be found in D8.1, however we can highlight the following:

- The robot navigation, localization and data capture proved to perform well. The SW modularity of RISING and Robotnik ground robot in general (with the same base architecture based in ROS) makes it possible to migrate to other ground vehicles with different features.
- The process of commanding inspection missions could benefit from colorized point clouds in order to identify the working areas in a better way. Reality capture all-in-one sensors can be seen as valuable option for this.

From these acknowledgements, it was decided that another ground robot from Robotnik could be brought on-site in order to gain experience and test different solutions. In this case, the RB-Watcher (see Figure 29) is well suited for inspection tasks and carries a Reality Capture solution (Leica BLK-ARC).

Figure 29. RB-Watcher robot.

The integration within the PILOTING system of both robot and sensor setup is straightforward given the similarities between both platforms. However, the integration has been validated again in a lab environment.

In the case of the tunnel with the CART robotic platform, the general inspection experiments were performed on two tunnels, first in a drainage tunnel for ease of preparation and lack of traffic, then in

the road tunnel with real traffic on a 60m distance area inside the tunnel. Aside of the details in D8.1 we can recall the overall picture as follows:

Similar tests were conducted for both general and local inspections using the main ground robot CART, with a separate section dedicated to drone tests. The experiments performed included robot capabilities and function verification, autonomous navigation, and inspection missions for image capturing and 3D laser scanning.

The results of testing the CART robotic system for navigation and inspection in both the road and drainage tunnel, highlight that the navigation system creates a map that is geometrically consistent with the environment and localization in existing maps works well. However, the system tends to underestimate the length of the traversed distance, resulting in a map that is approximately 10% shorter than manual measurements.

The autonomous navigation system was tested in basic missions and was successful in the road tunnel but struggled with the slope of the drainage tunnel. An additional challenge was introduced with the requirement for 1.5m steps to obtain images of the tunnel with enough overlapping for visual inspection, but the navigation system did not perform well in this task.

These issues addressed in the second iteration can be summarized as follow.

- Adjustments had to be made so that CART controller can perform better while drive in slopes in autonomous mode. This also helped to the continuous capturing as the capture trigger needed a smooth transition for each step. The SW calculations were improved in order to better interpolate the distances at which actions must be done.
- Positioning of the nav payload now considers shadows and inclination to maximize the field of view. **Sync of timestamps was a major issue that required strong integration effort.** The main action in this regard was configuring correctly the PTP sync between SINTEF payload and robot core and then integrating the map to robot transform. Also, a HW related action was issued relying on one single LIDAR (Ouster from SINTEF payload) for obstacle avoidance and wall following algorithm beyond the inherent localization functionality.
- Motor cycles for lifting column had to be taken into account depending on how the general inspection is covered, since robustness of the motor was at question. The continuous capturing procedure was also reducing this burden.
- Camera payload system robustness was reworked both HW and SW sides. The HW complexity was reduced by connecting directly to main machine (instead of wireless connection to a raspberry for acquisition). A depth sensor was also included for additional data. The acquisition and triggering on the SW were improved and different error regarding different lighting conditions were solved.

It is to be highlighted that due to the relevance of most of these enhancements and how they could affect the inspection process, an additional integration week was executed in Coripe tunnel (Seville, Spain), as shown in Figure 30, where the complete CART robotic inspection system was successfully validated (including the navigation and inspection subsystems).

Figure 30. CART robotic platform in Coripe tunnel during validation tests for integration.

On the other hand, for validating the integration of the UGV, the full inspection and manipulation pipeline was run in an end-to-end manner. A particular focus was set on making full use of the intended data pipeline and interfaces by not bypassing any step by manual intervention. In this way, it could be ensured that all interface implementations meet their expectations in the controlled target environment.

The details of the robot experiments are shown in D8.1. For the integration, in particular the following scenarios were validated successfully using the functionalities of the gRCS:

- Connection, disconnection and reconnection to the UGV under varying local network conditions.
- Check list download before mission, such as robot startup protocol.
- Path following and waypoint navigation.
- Autonomous valve manipulation using inspection points.
- Alert monitoring using the alert list, showing battery or camera alerts.
- High-level action execution, such as photo capturing.

Figure 31. gRCS view during Chevron Oronite mission showing successful connectivity and alarm list monitoring.

The successful validation of the integration of the UGV is in particular demonstrated by the fact that all experiments were repeated more than three times and the robot was fully commanded by means of the gRCS throughout all missions conducted on site. No intervention or emergency commanding by means of a fallback to the robot-specific mRCS was required for successful mission execution. This clearly shows that the implementation of the required, mission-critical functionalities and their interfaces is valid, stable and robust for on-site deployment.

Finally, it is important to mention that, also for UGV, a number of tests have been performed during the second integration phase to validate that everything was still working as in the first pilot experiments.

4.3 Crawlers and Hybrid Robots

The status of the integration of robotic crawler and hybrid platforms is as follows:

Table 3. Crawler and hybrid robot - gRCS integration status.

System	Heartbeat	Telemetry	Navigation	Command	Comments
BIKE	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 1 st cycle. Almost completely validated in 1 st pilots at Chevron Oronite (Sep 22). Fully integrated and validated during 2 nd integration cycle
HYBRID	✓	✓	✓	✓	Integrated in the 2 nd cycle. Same solution as AEROX and BIKE.

The basic integration of the BIKE platform with the PILOTING framework was validated in the field testing at the Chevron Oronite site in September 2022. There were however a few features missing and the final automated upload of the recorded mission data failed on the first attempts. The data was eventually successfully uploaded to the PILOTING portal.

The following remaining issues/actions were identified:

Table 4. BIKE identified issues from the first field validation testing in September 2022.

Issue	Description
1	BIKE was still unable to integrate actions (or tasks) directly from the planned mission into dedicated action-waypoints.
2	Actions could not be handled in a practical way in the gRCS software.
3	As a direct result from a), the data uploaded to the portal was not correctly associated to the mission tasks.
4	Placement of the robot at the beginning of the mission did not work reliably when invoked from the gRCS via the corresponding high-level command.
5	Mission upload to DDHL did not work.
6	Minor issues with graphical representation of asset in gRCS (point cloud resolution, labels sizes etc)

Details about how these issues were addressed are provided in section 3.1.1.

After successful testing of functionalities in separated experiments, a full validation experiment was conducted in the WTR vessel mockup during the second integration cycle.

The test mission contained relevant actions for visual testing (taking pictures of a dedicated area using the inspection camera), ultrasonic spot measurements and ultrasonic raster measurements. Figure 32 shows the tasks as planned in the portal and Table 5 gives the descriptions of the tasks.

Figure 32. BIKE validation mission in mockup asset.

Table 5. Inspection tasks for BIKE mission validation.

#	Description	Name	Inspection Type	Inspection Location
1	VT 1	Visual inspection 1	Visual inspection	Inspection Point 2
2	VT 2	Visual inspection 2	Visual inspection	Inspection part (N_Top_Front)
3	UT 1	Ultrasonic Inspection 1	Ultrasonic Inspection	Inspection Point 1
4	VT 3	Visual inspection 3	Visual inspection	Inspection part (N_Center)
5	UT Raster 1	Ultrasonic Inspection 2	Ultrasonic Inspection	Inspection Area 1
6	VT 4	Visual inspection 4	Visual inspection	Inspection Point 3

The validation included the following steps:

- 1) Download inspection plan and the environment model from portal to gRCS software by plan identifier.
- 2) Plan the waypoints in gRCS by directly using the tasks.
- 3) Download the inspection plan and the environment model from the portal to the robot specific control software by plan identifier.
- 4) Connect to robot control software from gRCS over the local network.
- 5) Execute the mission from gRCS using the autonomous BIKE – with interactions on robot specific software merely where the expert inspector is required (to capture the exact image location and record UT data once the robot had reached the location autonomously)

- 6) Upload the mission data from gRCS
- 7) Upload the mission data from robot control software.
- 8) Verify correct data in the PILOTING portal.

Figure 33 and Figure 34 show the mission data as it was uploaded to the PILOTING portal. The validation of the BIKE integration was successful. None of the issues from Table 4 were observed anymore.

Figure 33. Post-mission dashboard for BIKE validation testing.

Figure 34. Mission data in 3D on PILOTING portal, showing robot trajectory and locations of recorded images and thickness values.

Finally, and with respect to the HYBRID, it is important to highlight that it is a combination of two robotic systems, the aerial robot which main objective is the transportation and deployment of the second robot system, the Satellite system, that has a UT sensor incorporated. With respect to the integration, we have performed it separately. The HYBRID aerial robot integration solution is the same as the already integrated and validated for the AEROX (since both aerial platforms integrate the same SW architecture). Then, since the same on-board high-level SW as in AEROX is used, the integration with the gRCS and the robotic engine is straight forward, and it is already validated. In relation with the Satellite system, the integration solution is the same as the one just commented with the Bike, since both robots share the same high-level SW. Then, Satellite system integration is also straight forward, and it is already validated.

5. Conclusions

This document describes and completes the integration efforts of the robotic platforms within the PILOTING project. This document has been the continuation of deliverable D7.1, which was the first report of the first cycle of integration of the robotic platforms with the gRCS and the PILOTING ecosystem in general. The generalization of the communication interface of the robotic platforms with the gRCS has proved to be a success and allowed a smooth integration of all robots.

While in the first cycle the integration of the robotic platforms was more focused on simulation experiments to validate the software while the hardware integration was being completed, this second cycle has been more focused on the use of the final robots. This has allowed to validate many integrations that were initially tested at simulation level or in laboratory environments where elements were tested separately. In addition, the completion of the first pilots after the first integration cycle has served to start the second cycle with many of the features already tested in a real environment.

During this second cycle, the integration with gRCS has been performed mainly using a stable version of gRCS provided by CATEC. This has not only facilitated the integration of the robotic platforms in a more fluid and complete way, but has also served for the training and familiarization of the personnel with the software. Also, the reporting of possible errors found in the gRCS itself to the development team.

With respect to the robots, it has been shown that all the robotic systems have been successfully integrated. Then, all the presented work concludes the second integration cycle with all robotic platforms running gRCS and ready for the second iteration of the large-scale pilot demonstrations that will take place in WP8.